

Attitudes toward the Future and Depression Levels of Prospective Physical Education and Sports Teachers: A Mixed-Methods Study

Beden Eğitimi ve Spor Öğretmeni Adaylarının Geleceğe Yönelik Tutumları ve Depresyon Düzeyleri: Bir Karma Yöntem Araştırması

Aykut Şahin^{1*}, Burak Öner², Yunus Emre Karakaya³

*Correspondence:

Aykut ŞAHİN
aykutsahin@munzur.edu.tr
Orcid: 0000-0003-3654-6550

¹Munzur University, Faculty of Sport Sciences, Department of Physical Education and Sport, E-mail: aykutsahin@munzur.edu.tr
Orcid: 0000-0003-3654-6550

²Munzur University, Çemişgezek Vocational School, Department of Property Protection and Security, E-mail: burakoner@munzur.edu.tr
Orcid: 0000-0002-7390-4217

³Firat University, Faculty of Sport Sciences, Department of Physical Education and Sport Education, E-mail: emrekarakaya@firat.edu.tr
Orcid: 0000-0002-9858-2103

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18867628>

Received / Gönderim: 16.10.2025

Accepted / Kabul: 18.01.2026

Published / Yayın: 28.02.2026

Volume 3, Issue 1, February, 2026

Cilt 3, Sayı 1, Şubat, 2026

Abstract

This study was conducted to examine the relationship between attitudes toward the future and depression levels among prospective physical education and sports teachers. The study was conducted using a mixed-methods design. In the quantitative section, the "Burns Depression Scale" and the "Attitude toward Future Scale" were used on the study group. In the qualitative section, semi-structured interviews consisting of 5 questions were conducted on the study group. The quantitative findings of the study revealed that increased depression levels negatively affected prospective teachers' attitudes toward the future and that professional attitude significantly moderated this relationship. It was determined that prospective physical education and sports teachers who reported their professional attitude positively had lower depression levels and higher attitudes toward the future. Furthermore, it was concluded that the gender variable did not create a significant difference in depression and attitude toward the future. Qualitative findings revealed that professional values and commitment strengthened prospective teachers' hopes for the future. In contrast, economic uncertainties, appointment stress, and social expectations were shown to increase anxiety and negatively affect future planning. When evaluated within the framework of Expectancy-Value Theory and Cognitive Evaluation Theory, it was concluded that professional attitude functions as a motivational source, reduces the negative effects of depression, and increases prospective teachers' psychological resilience. The study shows that the negative relationship between prospective physical education and sports teachers' depression levels and their attitudes toward the future can be explained by professional attitudes and motivational mechanisms. These results emphasize the importance of designing teacher education programs with a focus on both psychological support and professional motivation. In conclusion, this study highlights the need for teacher education programs in higher education institutions to be structured in a way that supports both the professional motivation and psychological well-being of prospective teachers. In this context, guidance and counseling practices that reduce the effects of external factors such as appointment anxiety and economic uncertainties are also important.

Keywords Physical education, sports, prospective teacher, attitude toward future, depression

Özet

Bu çalışma, beden eğitimi ve spor öğretmen adaylarının geleceğe yönelik tutumları ile depresyon düzeyleri arasındaki ilişkiyi araştırmayı amaçlamıştır. Araştırma, karma yöntem tasarımı kullanılarak gerçekleştirilmiştir. Nicel kısımda, katılımcılara "Burns Depresyon Ölçeği" ve "Geleceğe Yönelik Tutum Ölçeği" uygulanmıştır. Nitel kısımda ise, katılımcılarla beş sorudan oluşan yarı yapılandırılmış görüşmeler yapılmıştır. Nicel bulgular, depresyon düzeylerindeki artışın adayların geleceğe yönelik tutumlarını olumsuz etkilediğini ve mesleki tutumun bu ilişkiyi önemli ölçüde yumuşattığını göstermiştir. Mesleki tutumlarını olumlu değerlendiren adayların daha düşük depresyon düzeyleri ve geleceğe yönelik tutumlarda daha yüksek puanlar sergiledikleri bulunmuştur. Ayrıca, cinsiyet değişkeni depresyon ve geleceğe yönelik tutumlarda önemli bir fark yaratmamıştır. Nitel bulgular, mesleğe verilen değer ve bağlılığın adayların geleceğe yönelik umutlarını artırdığını göstermiştir. Tersine, ekonomik belirsizlikler, atama stresi ve toplumsal beklentilerin kaygıyı artırdığı ve gelecek planlamasını olumsuz etkilediği gösterilmiştir. Beklenti-Değer Teorisi ve Bilişsel Değerlendirme Teorisi çerçevesinde, mesleki tutumun motivasyon kaynağı olarak işlev gördüğü, depresyonun olumsuz etkilerini hafiflettiği ve adayların psikolojik dayanıklılığını artırdığı sonucuna varılmıştır. Araştırma, beden eğitimi ve spor öğretmenliği adayları arasında depresyon düzeyleri ile geleceğe yönelik tutumlar arasındaki olumsuz ilişkinin mesleki tutum ve motivasyon mekanizmalarıyla açıklanabileceğini göstermektedir. Bu sonuçlar, hem psikolojik desteği hem de mesleki motivasyonu vurgulayan öğretmen eğitimi programları tasarlama önemini vurgulamaktadır. Sonuç olarak, bu çalışma, öğretmen adaylarının hem mesleki motivasyonunu hem de psikolojik iyilik halini desteklemek için yükseköğretim kurumlarında öğretmen eğitimi programlarının yapılandırılmasının gerekliliğini vurgulamaktadır. Bu bağlamda, atama kaygısı ve ekonomik belirsizlikler gibi dış faktörlerin etkilerini hafifletmeyi amaçlayan rehberlik ve danışmanlık uygulamaları da çok önemlidir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Beden eğitimi, spor, öğretmen adayı, geleceğe yönelik tutum, depresyon

<https://www.ijoss.org/Archive/v3-i1/ijoss-Volume3-issue1-05.pdf>

Introduction

The relationship between attitudes toward the future, depression, and professional attitudes plays an important role in understanding the pre-service development of prospective physical education and sports teachers toward the teaching profession. Indeed, the literature shows that prospective teacher perceptions of the future and motivational attitudes are directly related to depressive mood and professional identity development (Milton et al., 2018; Bryan & Solmon, 2007; Tessier et al., 2010). Depression, in particular, stands out as a factor that negatively affects prospective teachers' attitudes toward the future. However, the negative effects of depression on professional attitudes can be partially mitigated through prospective teachers' internalized motivation and professional identity development (Gunawardena et al., 2024; Tessier et al., 2010).

Expectancy-Value Theory (EVT) and Cognitive Evaluation Theory (CET) provide suitable theoretical frameworks for understanding the relationship between attitudes toward the future, depression, and occupational attitudes. EVT proposes that the effort individuals exert toward a task is determined by a combination of their expectancy of success and the value they assign to the task (Eccles et al., 1983; Eccles & Wigfield, 2002; Wigfield & Eccles, 2002). Individuals' past experiences, perceived abilities, beliefs, goals, and environmental factors influence both their expectations and task value, thereby shaping their motivation. In this context, prospective physical education and sports teachers' attitudes toward the profession constitute an important factor influencing their future expectations and motivation. High expectations and value perceptions reduce the negative effects of depression and support professional development and participation in innovative practices (Ball et al., 2019; Song & Jiang, 2019; Milton et al., 2018). CET (Deci & Ryan, 1985), in contrast, explains the basis of intrinsic motivation as the satisfaction of competence and autonomy needs. When these needs are met, motivation and psychological well-being are positively affected, whereas excessive external control reduces motivation. Within this framework, prospective teachers' motivation toward the profession, their expectations for the future, and their depressive feelings are evaluated theoretically. CET emphasizes that external stimuli, such as incentives, rewards, and punishments, that shape attitudes toward future regulate the effects of depression on professional attitudes and influence intrinsic motivation (Ntoumanis, 2001; Baker, 2004; Tessier et al., 2010). The perspectives presented in these theories provide important insight into understanding prospective teachers' experiences of depression and strengthening their professional attitudes.

Previous studies show that prospective teachers' professional identity development and leadership tendencies are directly linked to their attitudes toward future and depression levels (Dikmen & Tuncer, 2021; Huang & Wang, 2024; Ye et al., 2025). EVT-based studies indicate that expectations and value perceptions are decisive in prospective teachers' coping with their future anxieties and participating in innovative practices (Ball et al., 2019; Song & Jiang, 2019; Ashouri-Ahmadgoorabi et al., 2021). CET-based studies reveal that autonomy-supportive teaching climates and mastery-focused feedback increase prospective teachers' professional motivation and reduce the risk of burnout (Milton et al., 2018; Tessier et al., 2010). Moreover, the negative relationship between depression and attitudes toward the future has an indirect effect on prospective teachers' professional attitudes. Previous studies show that the direct negative effects of depression can be compensated for through professional attitude development processes, intrinsic motivation, and professional identity formation (Milton et al., 2018; Bryan & Solmon, 2007; Gunawardena et al., 2024).

Prospective physical education and sports teachers experience negative attitudes and depression toward the future in interaction with their personal motivation toward the profession. Autonomy- and competence-supportive educational environments, along with effective career guidance practices, mitigate the negative effects of depression while supporting attitudes toward the profession and adaptation to innovative pedagogical approaches (Milton et al., 2018; Bryan & Solmon, 2007; Ashouri-Ahmadgoorabi et al., 2021). Autonomy-supportive learning environments, structured feedback, and practices that increase intrinsic motivation regulate the negative effects of depression by increasing prospective teachers' intrinsic motivation (Ntoumanis, 2001; Baker, 2004; Tessier et al., 2010).

In this context, understanding prospective teachers' experiences of depression and developing their professional attitudes are important focuses for both individual and educational interventions. The main objective of this study is to explain the psychological and motivational mechanisms underlying the negative relationship between depression and attitudes toward the future among prospective physical education and sports teachers and to reveal how depression is regulated through professional attitudes. The study aims to examine these mechanisms in depth by using questions directed at the qualitative stage to complement the findings obtained from prospective teachers at the quantitative stage, within a mixed-methods framework. The study process aims to reveal the effects of depression on the relationship between attitudes toward the future and professional attitudes through questions shaped by EVT and CET theoretical frameworks.

In this context, the study sought answers to the following questions:

- What are the underlying psychological and motivational reasons for the negative relationship between attitudes toward the future and depression in the context of prospective teachers?
- How do prospective teachers interpret their experiences of depression and future-oriented anxieties, and how do these experiences shape their professional attitudes?
- Based on EVT, how do prospective teachers' expectations and value perceptions about the future play a role in explaining the relationship between depression and professional attitudes?
- Based on CET, how does the satisfaction of autonomy, competence, and relatedness needs regulate the effects of depression on professional attitudes?
- How does depression influence prospective teachers' professional attitudes through internalized motivation and professional identity development?

Hypotheses

- H1: There is a negative relationship between attitudes toward the future and depression. As depression levels increase, prospective teachers' attitudes toward the future are negatively affected (Milton et al., 2018; Bryan & Solmon, 2007).
- H2: Depression has a decisive effect on prospective teachers' professional attitude development process. The negative effects of depression are partially offset through mechanisms that develop a positive attitude toward the profession (Tessier et al., 2010; Gunawardena et al., 2024).
- H3: According to the EVT perspective, high achievement expectancy and high value perception help maintain and strengthen attitudes toward the

future by reducing the negative effects of depression (Ball et al., 2019; Song & Jiang, 2019).

- H4: According to the CET perspective, autonomy- and competence-supportive learning and guidance environments regulate the negative effects of depression on professional attitudes and increase intrinsic motivation (Ntoumanis, 2001; Baker, 2004; Tessier et al., 2010).
- H5: The mechanisms underlying the negative relationship between depression and attitudes toward the future can be explained by the processes involved in developing prospective teachers' professional attitudes. This process operates through internalized motivation and professional identity development.

Materials and Methods

It is stated that social science research involves complex problems and that using qualitative or quantitative designs alone may be insufficient to address this complexity (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2018; Johnson & Onwuegbuzie, 2004).. In this context, the exploratory sequential design from mixed methods was used in the study (Figure 1). The exploratory sequential design involves first collecting and analyzing quantitative data and then collecting qualitative data to gain a deeper understanding of the findings. This method allows for the evaluation of the effects of prospective physical education and sports teachers' attitudes toward the future on their depression levels from both quantitative and qualitative perspectives (Creswell, 2021). In this context, quantitative data were collected and analyzed by the researchers in the first phase of the study. In the second stage, qualitative data were collected and analyzed to gain an in-depth understanding of the problem situation in light of the quantitative results obtained. The correlational survey method was adopted for the quantitative part of the study, while the phenomenological research approach was adopted for the qualitative part.

Figure 1. Mixed research design workflow

Participants

In the quantitative section, the sample group of the study consists of 644 students studying at Munzur, Fırat, Bingöl, İnönü, and Erzincan Binali Yıldırım Universities in Turkey. The convenience sampling method, one of the non-random sampling types, was selected to form the sample group. The researchers' relationships with these universities and their ease of access were effective in selecting this sample group. Of the prospective physical education and sports teachers, 218 were female, and 426 were male. Of the

participants, 17.1% were first-year students, 19.7% were second-year students, 22.5% were third-year students, and 40.7% were fourth-year students.

In the qualitative section, the study was conducted with 22 students studying Physical Education and Sports Teaching at Firat University. Male students (68%) constituted the majority of the participants, while fourth-year students (45%) constituted the highest percentage according to class level. The ages of the participants ranged from 20 to 31 years, with the majority concentrated in the 22 to 23 age range (45%). Regarding teaching after graduation, half of the participants expressed a positive attitude (50%), while the other half expressed indecision or a negative opinion.

Data Collection Tools

Attitudes toward Future Scale (ATFS):

Developed by Bodur and Seren (2020), this is a Likert-type scale scored on a 1 to 5 range. All scale items consist of positive statements. The FOAS comprises four subscales, Thinking About and Planning for the Future, Positive Future Design/Optimism, Being Innovative, and Managing the Future, with a total of 21 items. It is accepted that as the scores obtained from the scale and its subscales increase, positive attitudes toward the future increase, and as the scores decrease, positive attitudes toward the future decrease. The goodness-of-fit values obtained from the Confirmatory Factor Analysis results were determined as follows: $C_{min}/df = 2.62$, $GFI = 0.93$, $AGFI = 0.91$, $NFI = 0.90$, $IFI = 0.93$, $TLI = 0.92$, $CFI = 0.93$, $RMSEA = 0.05$, $SRMR = 0.038$. Cronbach's alpha coefficients were calculated as 0.79 for Thinking About and Planning for the Future, 0.82 for Positive Future Design/Optimism, 0.69 for Being Innovative, 0.72 for Managing the Future, and 0.92 for the Attitude toward Future Scale.

Burns Depression Scale (BDS):

The Burns Depression Scale (BDS) was developed by David Burns in 1996 and adapted to the Turkish sample by Tuncer and Dikmen (2019). The BDS is a Likert-type scale scored on a 0 to 4 range. The ratings are None (0), Somewhat (1), Moderately (2), Very Much (3), and Extremely (4). The scale consists of six subscales, totaling 25 items. The subscales are named Activities and Personal Relationships, Feelings and Thoughts, Loss of Emotion, Suicidal Ideation, Physical Symptoms, and Health Problems. Higher scores on the scale and its subscales indicate higher levels of depression. The goodness-of-fit values obtained from the Confirmatory Factor Analysis results conducted in the current study are $C_{min}/df = 2.43$, $GFI = 0.92$, $AGFI = 0.90$, $NFI = 0.92$, $IFI = 0.95$, $TLI = 0.94$, $CFI = 0.95$, $RMSEA = 0.04$, $SRMR = 0.04$. Cronbach's alpha coefficients were determined as 0.85 for Activities and Personal Relationships, 0.86 for Feelings and Thoughts, 0.77 for Loss of Feelings, 0.87 for Suicidal Ideation, 0.73 for Physical Symptoms, 0.53 for Health Problems, and 0.93 for the Depression Scale.

Semi-Structured Interview Form:

As a qualitative data tool, a five-question semi-structured interview form was prepared and used by the researchers. The interviews were conducted by the researchers to explain the quantitative analysis results in depth and to understand the participants' attitudes toward the future. The questions were prepared based on EVT and CET.

EVT was developed by Jacquelynne Eccles and her colleagues (Eccles et al., 1983; Eccles & Wigfield, 2002; Wigfield & Eccles, 2002). This theory proposes that individuals' choices related to success are determined by the interaction between their expectations of success and the subjective task value they attribute to a particular domain. In other

words, when individuals believe they will be successful in an activity and attribute value to that activity, they are more likely to continue with it. The model addresses task value in four subscales: success value, the importance of being successful to the individual; intrinsic value, the pleasure or enjoyment derived from the activity; utility value, the usefulness of the activity in achieving future goals; and cost, the conflict that participation in the activity creates with other goals or activities. According to the Expectancy-Value model, individuals' expectations of success and perceptions of task value are shaped by the interaction of personal characteristics, such as abilities, past experiences, goals, self-perception, beliefs, and interpretations, and environmental factors, such as cultural context and the beliefs and behaviors of the social environment.

CET, developed by Deci and Ryan (1985), focuses on understanding individuals' motivation levels. The theory defines competence and autonomy as the fundamental determinants of intrinsic motivation. Competence refers to an individual's belief that they can succeed in the task at hand, while autonomy refers to the feeling that their actions are carried out of their own volition. According to the theory, satisfying these two needs positively affects individuals' motivation and mood, while external rewards or overly controlling factors can reduce intrinsic motivation. Thus, the theory explains how individuals evaluate events and the effect of these evaluations on motivation and psychological state (Deci & Ryan, 1985). Based on these theories, five questions were posed to prospective teachers.

The questions are as follows:

- How would you explain the effect of your thoughts about the future on your mood?
- How does your attitude toward your profession shape your expectations for the future?
- Does your perspective on the future change during periods when you feel depressed?
- Do you think your gender affects your concerns or hopes regarding your professional future?
- What changes did you experience in your mood during periods when your motivation toward your career was low?

Questions 2 and 4 are based on EVT, while Questions 1, 3, and 5 are based on CET.

Data Analysis

First, the normality assumption of the data obtained from both scales and their subscales was tested. According to the normality test performed using licensed SPSS 25 software, the skewness and kurtosis values were found to be between -1.5 and +1.5. Thus, the data were considered normally distributed, and the analysis continued using parametric tests. Independent samples t-tests and one-way ANOVA tests were applied to compare groups based on participants' demographic characteristics. The relationships among the subscales of the scales used were examined using Pearson's correlation test. Simple linear regression analysis was performed to determine the effect of participants' attitudes toward the future on their depression levels. Before proceeding to regression analysis, the linearity assumption was first evaluated using a scatter plot. Subsequently, the independence of errors was examined using the Durbin-Watson statistic for autocorrelation. It was concluded that both assumptions were appropriate for performing linear regression analysis. Qualitative data were analyzed using the thematic analysis method (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Statements obtained from the interview data were coded, and main themes related to the questions were established. This allowed for

an in-depth assessment of participants' attitudes toward the future in relation to their levels of depression.

Ethical Principles

Participation in the study was voluntary. Participants were informed about the purpose of the study and assured that the information they provided would be kept confidential. Participants' identity information was protected during the research process, and the data were used solely for scientific purposes. Information regarding the ethics committee decision within the scope of the study is as follows: The Ethics Committee of Firat University Social and Human Sciences Research unanimously decided that the study complies with ethical principles, with its decision dated 19.09.2025 and numbered 39238.

Results

In this section, the findings related to the quantitative and qualitative processes are presented.

Findings Related to Quantitative Phase

Table 1 presents the results of the analysis comparing participants' attitudes toward the future and depression by gender.

Table 1: Results of the analysis comparing participants' attitudes toward the future and depression by gender

Scale	Gender	N	M	SD	t	p
ATFS	Female	218	3.424	0.733	1.122	0.262
	Male	426	3.356	0.729		
BDS	Female	218	1.578	0.776	0.996	0.320
	Male	426	1.514	0.771		

The study group's attitudes toward the future and depression levels were compared according to gender, and the findings are presented in Table 1. Accordingly, no significant difference was found in attitudes toward future or depression levels of prospective physical education and sports teachers with respect to the gender variable ($p > 0.05$). In this context, it was concluded that gender is not a determining variable in terms of attitudes toward the future and depression. Table 2 presents the results of the analysis comparing participants' attitudes toward the future and depression according to professional attitude and grade level variables.

Table 2: Results of the analysis comparing participants' attitudes toward the future and depression according to professional attitude and grade level

Scale	Variable	N	M	SD	F	p	Significant Difference	
ATFS	Professional Attitude	(a) Poor	38	3.0827	0.6512	7.579	0.001*	c>a
		(b) Moderate	179	3.2671	0.7195			c>b
		(c) Good	427	3.4533	0.7312			
BDS	Professional Attitude	(a) Poor	38	2.0684	0.7366	11.781	0.000*	a>b
		(b) Moderate	179	1.5958	0.7494			a>c
		(c) Good	427	1.4637	0.7677			
ATFS	Grade	(a) 1 st Grade	110	3.3048	0.7949	1.878	0.132	
		(b) 2 nd Grade	127	3.5021	0.7286			
		(c) 3 rd Grade	145	3.3225	0.7299			
		(d) 4 th Grade	262	3.3835	0.7004			

BDS	(a) 1 st Grade	110	1.4215	0.7088	5.410	0.001*	c>a
	(b) 2 nd Grade	127	1.3868	0.8208			
	(c) 3 rd Grade	145	1.7250	0.7699			
	(d) 4 th Grade	262	1.5521	0.7587			

* p < 0.05

In the study, one-way analysis of variance and the Scheffe test were applied to determine whether professional attitudes and grade levels had a significant effect on attitudes toward future and depression among prospective physical education and sports teachers (Table 2). When total attitudes toward future scores were considered, the scores of the study group reporting good professional attitudes were significantly higher than those of the groups reporting moderate and poor professional attitudes ($F = 7.579$, $p < 0.01$). A positive perception of professional attitude was found to be a significant variable in terms of positive attitudes toward the future. Similarly, when the total depression level mean scores of the study group were examined, the scores of the group with poor professional attitudes were significantly higher than those of the groups reporting good and moderate professional attitudes ($F = 11.781$, $p < 0.001$). It was concluded that professional attitudes are an effective variable influencing depression levels among prospective physical education and sports teachers. No significant difference was found in attitudes toward the future according to grade level ($p > 0.05$). However, a significant difference was found in depression levels in the same analysis ($F = 5.410$, $p < 0.01$).

Table 3: Results of the simple linear regression analysis showing the effect of attitudes toward the future on depression

Model	Independent Variable	r	β	t	p	Model (p)	R ²
Model 1	Constant		-	24.993	<0.001	<0.001	0.07
	Attitude toward Future	-0.264	-0.264	-6.943	<0.001		

Durbin-Watson = 1.871; p < 0.001

A simple linear regression analysis was conducted to explain the effect of attitudes toward the future on depression levels in the study group (Table 3). According to the analysis results, 0.07 of the variance in depression levels was explained by attitudes toward the future ($R = 0.264$; $R^2 = 0.07$). According to Model 1, attitudes toward the future are a significant negative predictor of depression levels ($F = 48.200$, $p < 0.001$).

Findings Related to the Qualitative Phase

The qualitative data obtained from prospective teachers were evaluated, and the results are presented in tables.

Table 4: Thematic analysis of perceptions on the effect of attitudes toward the future on mood

Theme	Category	Example Participant Opinion	Relationship with the Theoretical Framework
Positive Effects	Goals and dreams as a source of motivation	PT-1: "Seeing that you have succeeded greatly affects your joy of living." PT-15: "By bringing my future dreams to mind, I continue my life with renewed excitement from where I left off."	EVT: Students' motivation increases as they attribute value to the future.
	The confidence that comes from being organized	PT-7: "When I look to the future, I have no concerns because I have been making plans for the future for the last three years."	Making plans for the future reduces anxiety and positively affects mood.
	Hope and optimism	PT-8: "I believe that I will fulfill the necessary requirements in the future."	CET: Individuals who evaluate the future positively have a stronger and more optimistic mood.
Negative Effects	Future anxiety and	PT-3: "The phrase 'You can't be appointed, you can't do it' affects our mood." PT-21: "My thoughts about the future make me anxious, and I often feel restless and unhappy."	CET: Evaluating events negatively leads to anxiety, stress, and indecision.

	uncertainty		
	Economic and social anxieties	PT-20: "Economic anxiety and the demands of society can make people feel sad."	Social expectations can negatively affect mood and trigger depressive feelings.
	Stress from the appointment and job search	PT-12: "There is stress associated with appointment, which negatively affects my mood." PT-22: "I am experiencing anxiety about whether I will be able to pursue my career and fulfill my duties adequately."	EVT: When the likelihood of success is perceived as low, motivation and mood are negatively affected.
Two-Way Effects	Both positive and negative effects	PT-9: "My goals positively affect my motivation, but sometimes they exhaust me and make me question myself." PT-19: "I feel happy when I dream, but I can become pessimistic when I think about the obstacles."	CET: Future assessments vary depending on the context; the same thought can generate both hope and anxiety.
	Mood-dependent variability	PT-10: "When I'm in a bad mood, I always think negatively about the future, but when I'm in a good mood, I think positively."	There is a cyclical relationship between mood and future expectations. Depressive mood increases negative perception.

A thematic analysis was conducted to evaluate the effect of prospective teachers' attitudes toward the future on their mood (Table 4). Prospective teachers experience future-related emotions in a bidirectional manner. On the one hand, focusing on the future serves as a source of hope and motivation, while on the other hand, it is associated with anxiety and stress. The most dominant negative theme identified in the study was future anxiety and appointment-related stress, whereas the most dominant positive theme was goals serving as a source of motivation. These findings are consistent with EVT and CET, indicating that individuals' expectations and evaluations directly shape their moods.

Table 5: Thematic analysis of the effect of professional attitudes on future expectations

Theme	Category	Example Participant View	Relationship with Theoretical Framework
Positive Attitude-Positive Expectations	Love and commitment to the profession-source of motivation	PT-1: "The reason I love teaching physical education is that this profession has character... I am taking steps with the awareness that I need to improve myself." PT-10: "I love my profession and am passionately committed to it; my expectations for the future are high and positive."	EVT: Individuals who value their profession have hopeful and high expectations for the future.
	Interaction with students and social contribution	PT-13: "Seeing children develop and educating them is exciting." PT-14: "Engaging in sports makes me happy, and I want to contribute to health through sports in the future."	Finding the role of teaching meaningful fosters a positive attitude toward the future.
	Alternative career paths (coaching, sports field)	PT-4: "The prospect of being able to work as a coach as well as a teacher after graduation has a positive impact on my hopes." PT-8: "As technology advances, the need for physical education teachers will increase due to people's sedentary lifestyles."	Viewing the profession as multidimensional brings about positive expectations for the future.
	Personal development and dedication	PT-16: "I am motivated by the desire to receive education, contribute something of myself, and pass on my knowledge in the future." PT-19: "When I set high expectations for myself, it affects my attitude and behavior, and I work harder."	CET: Those who view the future as an opportunity for personal development are more motivated.
Negative Attitude-Negative Expectations	Appointment issues and unemployment anxiety	PT-11: "The low number of appointments reduces motivation and productivity, so I am turning to different goals." PT-18: "I love teaching, but the appointment situation is dragging me into uncertainty."	EVT: When the likelihood of success is perceived as low, expectations decrease, and the tendency to turn to alternative plans increases.
	Uncertainty and disappointment	PT-2: "I have high expectations for the future, but I often think it could be worse." PT-15: "I love my profession, but I cannot form expectations for the future; it worries me."	Future expectations may vary depending on external conditions.
	Social/lack of recognition problem	PT-6: "Physical education is seen as a useless class, I want to show that it is an important class in the future." PT-22: "Because my profession is not valued as it should be, I want to be more careful and make a difference."	The perception of the subject as worthless negatively affects the perception of the profession, but at the same time creates motivation for change.
	Not loving the profession / turning to other fields	PT-7: "Physical education teaching is a profession I like, but it's not the profession I want to pursue; it doesn't change my expectations." PT-21: "At first, I dreamed of being a teacher, but now I want to open a Pilates studio."	A negative professional attitude gives rise to alternative career expectations.
Mixed/Conflic	Liking the profession	PT-15: "I love the profession, but I cannot form expectations for the future due to economic and political problems." PT-20: "My	CET: Attitudes toward the same profession can generate both positive and negative feelings.

ting Attitudes but being affected by economic/political conditions *view of the profession has not changed, but the decrease in the number of classes limits my future expectations."*

The thematic analysis findings regarding the effect of prospective teachers' professional attitudes on their expectations for the future are presented in Table 5. A significant proportion of prospective teachers develop positive and hopeful expectations for the future by attributing love and value to their profession. However, factors such as appointment anxiety, economic problems, and the insufficient perceived social value of the profession negatively affect these expectations. Some prospective teachers feel the need to pursue alternative career paths despite loving the profession due to these conditions. These findings are consistent with EVT; as the perceived value of the profession increases, future expectations strengthen, whereas expectations decrease when the perceived probability of success is low.

Table 6: Thematic analysis of the effect of depressive periods on perspectives about the future

Theme	Category	Example Participant View	Relationship with Theoretical Framework
Depression's Negative Impact on Future Perception	Increased Pessimism and Anxiety	<i>PT-5: "Those in a depressive state view the future pessimistically and anxiously." PT-14: "I feel depressed, my perspective is often pessimistic."</i>	CET: When mood is negative, the tendency to interpret future events negatively increases.
	Hopelessness and loss of motivation	<i>PT-18: "I don't want to make an effort for anything because I feel like I can't change the outcome." PT-21: "I am becoming more pessimistic about the future and I have no desire to do anything."</i>	Depression has a direct negative impact on motivation and future planning.
	Alternative plans / changing direction	<i>PT-12: "I tend to think about the possibility that my future plans may not come true and turn to different areas." PT-22: "When I give up, I have different thoughts, such as drawing a different path, but then I return to what I really want."</i>	EVT: When expectations of success are perceived as low, individuals reshape their motivation by considering alternative paths.
Strategies to Limit the Effects of Depression	Self-motivation and returning to a positive outlook	<i>PT-1: "...I tend to give up, but I immediately lift my mood and redirect it toward my goal." PT-3: "I work harder and more determinedly during bad times."</i>	CET: Negative mood is temporary and can be consciously managed by the individual.
	Controlling emotions and persevering	<i>PT-6: "No matter how bad I feel, my perspective doesn't change." PT-8: "I don't allow my perspective to change; I keep going until the end."</i>	Some teacher candidates limit the effects of depression to protect their plans.
Situational/Conflicting Effects	Both positive and negative effects	<i>PT-4: "During depressive periods, I view the future negatively, but after recovering, I can look at it with more hope." PT-2: "I have high expectations, but I often think things could get worse; still, I can't stop and make plans."</i>	The outlook for the future changes during depressive periods, but the situation is temporary and balanced by motivation.
	The influence of age and social conditions	<i>PT-9: "...due to our age and country conditions, in some periods, we fall into despair, thoughts of failure, negativity..."</i>	Individuals' social environment and age group affect their outlook on the future during depressive periods.

A thematic analysis was conducted on changes in prospective teachers' perspectives about the future during depressive periods (Table 6). Depressive periods create pessimism, anxiety, and loss of motivation regarding the future for most prospective teachers. However, some prospective teachers can limit these negative effects through conscious strategies such as self-motivation and maintaining their plans. These effects are generally temporary and vary depending on individuals' mood states. In addition, social and life conditions, such as national circumstances and age group, may intensify the negative effects of depression on future perspectives.

Table 7: Thematic analysis of the effect of gender on professional future

Theme	Category	Example Participant View	Relationship with Theoretical Framework
	Concerns of female candidates	<i>PT-15: "The value given to women is insufficient, not being seen as equal, being looked down upon... this situation makes me feel hopeless and anxious." PT-19: "The prevalence of sexism negatively</i>	EVT: The restrictive roles imposed on women by society increase occupational anxiety.

Negative Impact of Gender		<i>affects my goals and expectations as a woman."</i>	
	Social responsibility and burden	<i>PT-5: "Men bear more responsibility for having a career and providing for their families." PT-21: "As a woman, I am anxious because not being able to study the subject I want and start a career is sad and disappointing."</i>	Social roles create anxiety through gender-based expectations and responsibilities.
Positive or Limited Impact of Gender	The perception that gender does not create professional barriers	<i>PT-1: "I am moving towards my goal without associating it with gender in any way." PT-6: "Our profession is equal for women and men, so there is no anxiety."</i>	Some teacher candidates do not experience anxiety because they do not evaluate the profession in terms of gender differences.
	Physical and skill-based advantages	<i>PT-2: "As a man, I have mental and physical aptitudes, but women can also have them, so I have no concerns." PT-14: "My gender is not an obstacle to my professional future; it can be an advantage."</i>	Social perception can sometimes interpret gender as a positive advantage.
Mixed/Situational Effects	Effects that vary depending on the profession, society, and field	<i>PT-4: "Gender is irrelevant in teaching, but being male can be problematic in coaching." PT-22: "Today, women are strong and supported in sports, and concerns are diminishing."</i>	The social context and professional field determine the impact of gender; perceptions change over time and depending on circumstances.

The thematic analysis findings regarding how prospective teachers' gender shapes their attitudes toward their professional future are presented in Table 7. Some female prospective teachers experience professional anxiety stemming from gender roles. In contrast, male prospective teachers generally evaluate the effect of gender on professional processes as positive or neutral. The effect of gender varies according to the professional and branch context. In some cases, it provides advantages, while in others, it may be limiting. Over time and with social change, gender-related anxieties appear to show a decreasing trend.

Table 8: Thematic analysis of the effect of decreased professional motivation on mood

Theme	Category	Example Participant View	Relationship with the Theoretical Framework
Negative Mood and Increased Anxiety	Feeling Depressed and Pessimistic	<i>PT-6: "There have been times when I felt bad, unmotivated, unenthusiastic, and hopeless." PT-15: "I see myself as inadequate, incompetent, and someone who will never amount to anything in life."</i>	CET: Low motivation negatively affects the individual's assessment of the future and disrupts their mood.
	Anxiety, stress, and hopelessness	<i>PT-10: "...anxiety, hopelessness, aggression, negative thinking..." PT-19: "Low motivation negatively affects my mood, leading me to pessimism and inaction."</i>	Low motivation has a direct negative impact on emotional state.
Positive or Compensatory Strategies	Self-motivation and creating hope	<i>PT-1: "...when my motivation drops, I feel emotionally bad, but I immediately pull myself out by finding new hope." PT-11: "I want to love my job and try to motivate myself."</i>	EVT: Expectations and perceptions of value regarding the future help individuals shift their mood back to positive, even if their motivation declines.
	Alternative paths and problem-solving	<i>PT-8: "...I try to find a second and third job, I get caught up in thoughts of securing myself." PT-22: "...I withdraw into my shell, evaluate myself, and then become motivated."</i>	Low motivation can be balanced with planning and problem-solving behaviors.
Situational Effects / Social Conditions	Assignment, economic, or system-related effects	<i>PT-4: "...I experience a depressive mood in the example of the profession, my anxieties may increase..." PT-8: "...seeing low assignments or those who get ahead through social media..."</i>	Social and systemic factors shape the effects on motivation and mood.
The Temporary Nature of Negative Mood	Recovery after motivation declines	<i>PT-16: "...I try to motivate myself and focus on my goal." PT-22: "...even if the process is negative, it has a positive effect on my overall thinking and behavior afterwards, making me more motivated."</i>	Negative mood is temporary and can be compensated for with conscious strategies, allowing individuals to regain their motivation.

The thematic analysis evaluating the effect of low motivation toward the teaching profession on mood is presented in Table 8. For most prospective teachers, decreased motivation leads to pessimism, anxiety, stress, and negative emotions. However, some participants can limit negative mood states through strategies such as self-motivation, generating hope, and developing alternative plans. The findings indicate that systemic and social conditions, particularly appointment status, economic uncertainties, and social perceptions, affect prospective teachers' motivation and mood. Nevertheless,

these negative effects are generally temporary, and prospective teachers are able to compensate for them through conscious strategies.

Discussion and Conclusion

The quantitative and qualitative findings obtained using mixed methods in this study show that prospective teachers' experiences of depression shape their attitudes toward the future and their professional attitudes under certain conditions. Quantitative analyses revealed a significant negative relationship between depression and attitudes toward the future. Indeed, the existence of this negative relationship has been examined in several studies (Bjärehed et al., 2010). As the level of depression increases, prospective teachers' attitudes toward the future are negatively affected. This finding confirms the results reported by Milton et al. (2018) and Bryan and Solmon (2007). These studies likewise indicate that prospective teachers' psychological well-being is a decisive factor in their hope and planning behaviors regarding the future. Simple linear regression analyses support the H1 hypothesis by revealing that attitudes toward the future are a significant negative predictor of depression levels.

The decisive effect of professional attitude on both attitudes toward the future and depression confirms hypothesis H2. Quantitative data show that prospective teachers who evaluate their professional attitude as good have low depression scores and high attitudes toward future scores. This finding indicates that professional identity and commitment are important factors that strengthen the psychological resilience of prospective teachers. Qualitative data directly link prospective teachers' love for and appreciation of the profession with their hopes and expectations for the future. However, external factors such as appointment anxiety, economic uncertainty, and the social perception of the profession are observed to have negative effects. These findings are consistent with the concept of task value proposed within EVT. As the perceived value of the profession increases, attitudes toward the future strengthen, whereas these attitudes are negatively affected when the likelihood of success is perceived to be low (Eccles et al., 1983; Ball et al., 2019; Song & Jiang, 2019).

Qualitative analyses conducted within the framework of EVT and CET show that prospective teachers experience their future in two ways. On the one hand, goals serve as a source of motivation. On the other hand, anxiety and stress emerge as triggering factors for depression. This situation parallels the perspective of CET, which posits that satisfying autonomy and competence needs improves motivation and psychological well-being (Deci & Ryan, 1985; Ntoumanis, 2001). In particular, the finding that low motivation is directly related to depression and negative mood, but can be compensated for through conscious strategies and planning, supports the idea that prospective teachers can regulate the negative effects of depression through intrinsic motivation and professional identity development. This finding confirms hypothesis H5.

The finding that gender did not significantly affect attitudes toward future or depression levels is partially consistent with the existing literature (Milton et al., 2018; Bryan & Solmon, 2007). Qualitative findings indicate that gender roles may influence professional concerns in some situations. However, professional attitudes and individual motivation play a role in balancing this effect. This result highlights the need for educational programs to provide psychological and professional support for both female and male prospective teachers.

When evaluated based on EVT and CET, hypotheses H3 and H4 are supported. High achievement expectancy and high value perception reduce the negative effects of depression and protect attitudes toward the future. Autonomy and competence in supportive educational and mentoring environments regulate the negative effects of

depression on professional attitude and increase intrinsic motivation. These results emphasize the reciprocal relationship between prospective teachers' psychological well-being and their professional motivation and attitudes (Ball et al., 2019; Song & Jiang, 2019; Ntoumanis, 2001; Baker, 2004; Kaya & Çenesiz, 2020).

Furthermore, qualitative findings indicate that prospective teachers develop conscious strategies to cope with depression and negative mood. This suggests that the process of developing professional attitudes is an important mechanism for limiting the negative effects of depression. Therefore, it is understood that both individual and educational interventions should be designed to support prospective teachers' intrinsic motivation and professional identity development (Tessier et al., 2010; Gunawardena et al., 2024; Ashouri-ahmadgoorabi et al., 2021).

The study reveals that the negative relationship between prospective physical education and sports teachers' depression levels and their attitudes toward the future can be explained by professional attitudes and motivational mechanisms. When evaluated within the framework of EVT and CET, prospective teachers' expectations of success, task values, and perceptions of autonomy and competence reduce the negative effects of depression and strengthen their professional attitudes. These results emphasize the importance of designing teacher education programs with a focus on both psychological support and professional motivation.

The study results highlight the importance of structuring teacher education programs in a manner that increases prospective teachers' psychological resilience and professional motivation. Autonomy-supported learning environments, mastery-focused feedback, and goal-setting strategies can be effective in reducing the negative effects of depression. Furthermore, designing programs for professional attitude and identity development that support prospective teachers' positive attitudes toward the future will increase teachers' long-term professional motivation. In this context, guidance and counseling practices that reduce the effects of external factors such as appointment anxiety and economic uncertainties are also important.

Kısaltmalar / Abbreviations

SD	Standart sapma (Standard deviation)
M	Ortalama (Mean)
SPSS	Sosyal bilimler için istatistik paketi (Statistical package for the social sciences)
p value	Anlamlılık değeri (Significant value)
t value	T değeri (T value)
F	F değeri (F value)
N	Katılımcı sayısı (Number of participant)
EVT	Expectancy-Value Theory
CET	Cognitive Evaluation Theory
ATFS	Attitudes toward Future Scale
BDS	Burns Depression Scale

Beyanlar / Declarations

Etik Onay ve Katılım Onayı / Ethics approval and consent to participate

Bu çalışmanın hazırlanması ve yazılması sırasında, "Yükseköğretim Kurumları Bilimsel Araştırma ve Yayın Etiği Kılavuzları"na uygun olarak bilimsel, etik ve alıntı kurallarına uyulmuştur; toplanan verilerde herhangi bir değişiklik yapılmamıştır ve bu çalışma başka hiçbir akademik yayın organına değerlendirme için sunulmamıştır. Bu makaleyle ilgili olarak ortaya çıkabilecek her türlü ihalden yazar tek başına sorumludur. Çalışmaya katılım gönüllülük esasına dayanmaktadır. Katılımcılara çalışmanın amacı hakkında bilgi verilmiş ve sağladıkları bilgilerin gizli tutulacağına dair güvence verilmiştir. Araştırma süreci boyunca katılımcıların kimlik bilgileri korunmuş ve veriler yalnızca bilimsel amaçlarla kullanılmıştır. Çalışma kapsamında etik kurul kararı ile ilgili bilgiler aşağıdaki gibidir: Fırat Üniversitesi Sosyal ve Beşeri Bilimler Araştırma Etik Kurulu, 19.09.2025 tarihli ve 39238 sayılı kararı ile çalışmanın etik ilkelere uygun olduğuna oybirliği ile karar vermiştir.

During the preparation and writing of this study, scientific, ethical and citation rules were followed in accordance with the 'Higher Education Institutions Scientific Research and Publication Ethics Guidelines'; no alterations were made to the collected data, and this study has not been submitted for evaluation to any other academic publication medium. The author is solely responsible for any violations that may arise in connection with this article. Participation in the study was voluntary. Participants were informed about the purpose of the study and assured that the

information they provided would be kept confidential. Participants' identity information was protected during the research process, and the data were used solely for scientific purposes. Information regarding the ethics committee decision within the scope of the study is as follows: The Ethics Committee of Firat University Social and Human Sciences Research unanimously decided that the study complies with ethical principles, with its decision dated 19.09.2025 and numbered 39238.

Veri Ve Materyal Erişilebilirliği / Availability of data and material

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request. The dataset will be accessible only for academic purposes, and any use of the data will recognize the original study and maintain the confidentiality of the participants.

Çıkar Çatışması / Competing interests

Yazarlar, bu makalede sunulan çalışmayı etkileyebilecek herhangi bir çıkar çatışması veya kişisel ilişkiye sahip olmadıklarını beyan etmektedirler.

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Yazar Katkıları / Authors' Contribution Statement

Çalışmanın tasarımı ve planlanması: A.Ş., Y.E.K.; Veri toplama, analizi veya yorumlanması: A.Ş., B.Ö., Y.E.K.; Makalenin yazımı: A.Ş., B.Ö., Y.E.K.; Veri düzenleme, yöntem belirleme, yazım – özgün taslak, yazım – gözden geçirme ve düzenleme: A.Ş., B.Ö.; Tüm yazarlar, makalenin önemli noktalarını eleştirel bir şekilde gözden geçirmiştir. Tüm yazarlar makalenin son halini onaylamıştır. /

Design and planning of the study: A.Ş., Y.E.K.; Data collection, analysis or interpretation: A.Ş., B.Ö., Y.E.K.; Manuscript preparation A.Ş., B.Ö., Y.E.K.; Data organization, methodology development, writing - original draft, writing – review and editing: A.Ş., B.Ö.; All authors critically reviewed the key points of the manuscript and approved the final version.

Fon Desteği / Funding

This Bu çalışma, kamu, özel veya kar amacı gütmeyen sektörlerdeki fon sağlayıcı kurumlardan herhangi bir özel destek almamıştır.

This research received no external funding.

Teşekkür / Acknowledgements

None.

References / Kaynaklar

- Ashouri-ahmadgoorabi, R., Rouhani-Tonekaboni, N., Kasmaei, P., Shakiba, M., & Kamalikhah, T. (2021). Physical activity determinants of female teachers in rasht county, iran; applying the social cognitive theory. *Journal of Education and Community Health*, *8*(2), 89-96. <https://doi.org/10.52547/jech.8.2.89>
- Baker, S. (2004). Intrinsic, extrinsic, and amotivational orientations: their role in university adjustment, stress, well-being, and subsequent academic performance. *Current Psychology*, *23*(3), 189-202. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-004-1019-9>
- Ball, C., Huang, K. T., Rikard, R. V., & Cotten, S. R. (2019). The emotional costs of computers: An expectancy-value theory analysis of predominantly low-socioeconomic status minority students' STEM attitudes. *Information, Communication & Society*, *22*(1), 105-128. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1369118x.2017.1355403>
- Bjärehed, J., Sarkohi, A., & Andersson, G. (2010). Less positive or more negative? Future-directed thinking in mild to moderate depression. *Cognitive behaviour therapy*, *39*(1), 37-45.
- Bodur, G., & Seren, A. K. H. (2020). Geleceğe Yönelik Tutum Ölçeğinin geliştirilmesi ve Türk toplumunda geçerlilik ve güvenilirliğinin değerlendirilmesi. *Anadolu Psikiyatri Dergisi*, *21*, 5-13. <http://doi.org/10.5455/apd.69856>
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, *3*(2), 77-101. <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp063oa>
- Bryan, C. L., & Solmon, M. A. (2007). Self-determination in physical education: designing class environments to promote active lifestyles. *Journal of Teaching in Physical Education*, *26*(3), 260-278. <https://doi.org/10.1123/jtpe.26.3.260>
- Creswell, J. W., & Plano Clark, V. L. (2018). *Designing and conducting mixed methods research* (3rd ed.). Sage Publications.
- Creswell, J.W. (2021). *Karma yöntem araştırmalarına giriş* (3. bs.) (M. Sözbilir, Çev.). Pegem Akademi. (Orijinal basım tarihi 2017). <https://DOI.14527/9786053184720>
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (1985). *Intrinsic Motivation and Self-Determination in Human Behavior*. Berlin: Springer Science & Business Media. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4899-2271-7>

- Dikmen M., & Tuncer M., (2021). Investigation of Pre-Service Teachers' Depression Levels, Teaching Motivations and Their Attitudes towards Profession. *Journal of Higher Education and Science*, 11(2), 401-410. <https://doi.org/10.5961/jhes.2021.459>
- Eccles, J. S., & Wigfield, A. (2002). Motivational beliefs, values, and goals. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 53(1), 109–132. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.psych.53.100901.135153>
- Eccles, J. S., Adler, T. F., Futterman, R., Goff, S. B., Kaczala, C. M., Meece, J. L., & Midgley, C. (1983). *Expectancies, values, and academic behaviors*. In J. T. Spence (Ed.), *Achievement and achievement motives: Psychological and sociological approaches* (pp. 75–146). W. H. Freeman.
- Gunawardena, H., Leontini, R., Nair, S., Cross, S., & Hickie, I. (2024). Teachers as first responders: classroom experiences and mental health training needs of Australian schoolteachers. *BMC Public Health*, 24(1), 268. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-023-17599-z>
- Huang, X., & Wang, C. (2024). Pre-service teachers' professional identity transformation: a positioning theory perspective. *Professional Development in Education*, 50(1), 174–191. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19415257.2021.1942143>
- Johnson, R. B., & Onwuegbuzie, A. J. (2004). Mixed methods research: A research paradigm whose time has come. *Educational Researcher*, 33(7), 14–26. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0013189X033007014>
- Kaya, Z., & Çenesiz, G. Z. (2020). The predictor roles of life-satisfaction, and intrinsic-extrinsic motivation on the psychological well-being of pre-service teachers. *International Online Journal of Education and Teaching*, 7(4), 1370-1387.
- Milton, D., Appleton, P. R., Bryant, A., & Duda, J. L. (2018). Initial validation of the teacher-created empowering and disempowering motivational climate questionnaire in physical education. *Journal of Teaching in Physical Education*, 37(4), 340-351. <https://doi.org/10.1123/jtpe.2018-0119>
- Ntoumanis, N. (2001). A self-determination approach to the understanding of motivation in physical education. *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, 71(2), 225-242. <https://doi.org/10.1348/000709901158497>
- Song, J., & Jiang, Y. (2019). The distinct roles of proximal and distal utility values in academic behaviors: future time perspective as a moderator. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10, 1061. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.01061>
- Tessier, D., Sarrazin, P., & Ntoumanis, N. (2010). The effect of an intervention to improve newly qualified teachers' interpersonal style, students motivation and psychological need satisfaction in sport-based physical education. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 35(4), 242-253. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cedpsych.2010.05.005>
- Tuncer, M., & Dikmen, M. (2019). The Reliability and Validity of Turkish Form of the Burns Depression Scale. *Journal of Social and Humanities Sciences Research*, 6(42), 2848-2857. doi:10.26450/jshsr.1429
- Wigfield, A., & Eccles, J. S. (2002). The development of competence beliefs, expectancies for success, and achievement values from childhood to adolescence. In A. Wigfield & J. S. Eccles (Eds.), *Development of achievement motivation* (pp. 91–120). Academic Press. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-012750053-9/50006-1>
- Ye, X., Cheng, T., & Yang, W. (2025). Learning Engagement and Professional Identity Among Pre-Service Teachers: The Sequential Mediating Role of Adaptability and Self-Concept. *Behavioral Sciences*, 15(7), 881. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bs15070881>

Publishers' Note

IJOSS remains neutral with regard to jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations.